

STUDIES ON VITAMIN-A IN SOLUTION. PART II. MODE OF ACTION OF THE ANTIOXIDANT

BY U. P. BASU AND SUKHAMOY BHATTACHARYA

An attempt has been made to explore the mode of action of a hydroxy-phenolic antioxidant in retarding the onset of oxidation in vitamin-A molecule.

Vitamin-A (I) is an unsaturated alcohol and in pure crystalline form it has been found to melt at 63-64°. But in its natural form it is present both in the free alcoholic and in an ester (palmitate) form (Tischer, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1938, 125, 475). Recently Robeson and Baxter (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 136) have again shown that certain shark-liver oils contain up to 35% of the total vitamin in a form which is a *trans-cis* isomer of the normal vitamin (*trans-trans* variety). The two isomers differ in the spacial configuration about the double bond nearest the hydroxyl group, the *trans-cis* being more resistant than the normal one. Similarly the observations of Baxter and Robeson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2407) and that of Basu and Sen Gupta (*ibid.*, 1948, 70, 413) tend to show that whether in natural form or in the artificial fortified food, the vitamin ester is more resistant than the free alcohol to atmospheric oxidation. This oxidative change may be considerably controlled by incorporation of a suitable antioxidant (cf. Whipple, *Oil & Soap*, 1936, 13, 231; Lowen, Anderson and Harrison, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1937, 29, 151; Basu, *Ann. Biochem. Exp. Med.*, 1941, 1, 165). As the vitamin is usually present in some fat or oil, this oxidation is believed to be due to an onset of oxidation in the unsaturated molecule of the latter substance. An earlier observation of Basu (*loc. cit.*) indicates that the deterioration of the vitamin-A cannot be accounted for by the above change only. Vitamin-A itself is an unsaturated body with five unsaturated bonds, four in the aliphatic side chain and one in the ionone ring. It is not entirely clear whether the relation of unsaturation to physiological activity resides solely in the β -ionone ring or whether some unsaturation in the side chain is also important. The unsaturated bond in the β -ionone ring is oxidisable to an epoxide (II) under the influence of perphthalic acid (Karrer and Jucker, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, 28, 717; 1947, 30, 559) and the alcoholic group also undergoes oxidation to vitamin-A aldehyde (III) when heated with aluminium isopropoxide in the presence of acetaldehyde (Hawkin and Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 411). Hunter and Krakenberger (*ibid.*, 1947, 1) have recently shown that β -carotene, the precursor of vitamin-A, undergoes oxidation in solution by oxygen to β -carotene epoxide (of the type II) which subsequently undergoes fission to give rise to an open-chain ketone. Vitamin-A also under the action of ozone yields geronic acid (IV). Whatever may be the product or products of oxidation, it is a fact that the unsaturated bonds readily absorb oxygen in solution and are markedly pro-oxygenic in nature. Highly oxidised vitamin-A has no biological activity too, and as such if the inherent cause and mode of oxidation be known, it would be much easier to control the deterioration of the vitamin during isolation (cf. Rao, *Ind. J. Med. Res.*,

antioxidant in this case also by preventing the formation of hydro-peroxide helps in protecting the vitamin from deterioration. As the ester or glyceride has been further found to inhibit the onset of oxidation, it may be argued that the ester by incipient formation of an acid-like body is either forming a complex with the vitamin molecule, or, is helping the continuity of hydroxy antioxidant in the system. In order to find out the role of the antioxidant in preventing the deterioration of vitamin-A molecule further work has been continued and the results of these observations have been recorded in the body of this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nature of the Antioxidant.—Hydroquinone containing two hydroxyl groups is a good antioxidant for vitaminised oil (Basu, *loc. cit.*). In the course of this investigation monomethyl ether of hydroquinone (m.p. 54-56°), dimethyl ether of hydroquinone (m.p. 54-55°) and propyl gallate (m.p. 146-48°) were prepared. They are soluble in oils and esters. In case of propyl gallate, which is not readily soluble in liquid paraffin, the antioxidant was first dissolved in a few drops of peroxide-free ether and the solution was mixed with liquid paraffin. Each of mono and dimethyl ether of hydroquinone was dissolved in 25 c.c. of ethyl oleate containing 740 I.U. of vitamin-A per g. in an amber coloured resistant bottle fitted with perforated corks for aeration under negative pressure. The concentration of both the antioxidants in the preparation was 0.05%. Samples were withdrawn at intervals and the vitamin-A contents were estimated by the procedure as laid down in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). The results are shown in Table I.

Role of Oleic Acid in Liquid Paraffin System.—The characteristic behaviour of esters in vitamin-A preparations indicates that a simple acid molecule may also play a similar role in protecting vitamin-A from oxidation. With this idea in view three preparations, each containing 1100 I.U. of vitamin-A per g., were made in (i) simple liquid paraffin (25 c.c.) ; (ii) in liquid paraffin (25 c.c.) containing 0.05% propyl gallate, and (iii) in liquid paraffin containing 0.05% propyl gallate and 0.14% oleic acid. Dry and purified air was passed and samples were withdrawn and assayed for vitamin-A in the customary way. Results are recorded in Table II.

Influence of Water in Liquid Paraffin System.—Preparation of vitamin-A containing 1100 I.U. per g. was made with liquid paraffin and water (liquid paraffin : water = 1:2) was added to it in presence of 0.05% propyl gallate. The system was aerated and as it was difficult to withdraw representative sample of the mixture, the whole after 191 hours' aeration was extracted with peroxide-free ether (thrice with 50 c.c. portions). The volume was reduced to about 50 c.c. by evaporation of ether and again the volume was made up to 100 c.c. with ether in a volumetric flask. An aliquot part of this solution was taken for vitamin-A assay. The results are shown in the last two columns of Table II.

Peroxide Formation in Vitamin-A.—Two preparations containing 1100 I.U. of vitamin-A per g. were made from vitamin-A concentrate in liquid paraffin, one being without the addition of any antioxidant and the other with 0.05% propyl gallate. Both were aerated and the peroxide formed was determined at intervals according to Basu and Mazumder (*Leprosy in India*, 1939, 11, 53). The peroxide value has been

expressed as the number of c.c. of 0.002*N*-sodium thiosulphate per g. of the preparation (vide Table III).

Deterioration in Vitamin-A Acetate.—Two gelatin capsules of vitamin-A acetate each containing 2500 U.S.P. units of vitamin-A were taken in 10 c.c. of ethyl oleate of the specification described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). The tips of the capsules were cut with fine scissors and the contents were well mixed and the vitamin-A potency of the solution was on analysis found to contain 570 I.U. per g. (this is equivalent to 496 I.U. per ml, theoretically it should have been 500 I.U. per c.c.). A similar preparation was made with ethyl stearate of the specification described in the previous paper and on assay was found to contain 513 I.U. of vitamin-A per g.

This showed that vitamin-A acetate did not undergo any initial loss of potency when dissolved in fatty esters unlike the free vitamin-A alcohol molecule. Both the preparations were then subjected to aeration (4 c.c. per second) with purified and dried air. Samples were withdrawn at intervals and assayed for vitamin-A content. The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE I

Ethyl oleate.

Duration of aeration	Without antioxidant.		With 0.05% dimethyl hydroquinone		With 0.05% monomethyl hydroquinone	
	Vitamin-A (I. U /g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A	Vitamin-A (I. U /g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A	Vitamin A (I U /g)	% Loss of vitamin A.
0 hr.	740	0	740	0	740	0
52	300	59.5	—	—	—	—
59	—	—	282	61.9	—	19.6
66	—	—	—	—	595	—
94	196	73.5	—	—	—	—
100	—	—	193	74.0	535	27.7
149	190	74.3	—	—	—	—
160	—	—	—	—	513	30.7
177	—	—	184	75.1	—	—

TABLE II

Liquid paraffin.

Duration of aeration.	Without antioxidant.		With 0.05% propyl gallate		With 0.05% propyl gallate + 0.14% oleic acid		With 0.05% propyl gallate + water.	
	Vitamin-A (I. U /g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A	Vitamin-A (I U /g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A	Vitamin-A (I U /g.)	% loss of vitamin-A	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% loss of vitamin-A.
0 hr	1100	0	1100	0	1100	0	1100	0
87	512	53.5	658	40.2	773	29.7	—	—
142	305	72.3	620	43.7	755	31.4	—	—
191	222	79.8	610	44.6	750	31.8	800	27.3

TABLE III

Peroxide formation of vitamin-A alcohol in liquid paraffin
 Conc. of vitamin-A = 1100 I.U./g.

Duration-of aeration.	Without antioxidant Peroxide value (ml. of 0.002N-thio per g.)	With 0.05% propyl gallate. Peroxide value (ml. of 0.002N-thio per g.)
0 hr.	Nil	Nil
134	1.91	
180	3.10	0.75
ii.		

TABLE IV

Vitamin-A acetate system without antioxidant.

Duration of aeration.	Vitamin-A acetate in ethyl oleate.		Vitamin-A acetate in ethyl stearate.	
	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0 hr.	570	0	513	0
80	420	24.7	416	18.9
135	423	25.8	—	—
142	—	—	390	24.0
184	—	—	340	33.7
190	410	28.1	—	—

TABLE V

Loss of vitamin-A in various systems.

Systems.	Vitamin-A alcohol			
	Duration of aeration.	Without antioxidant.	Duration of aeration.	With antioxidant
Arachis oil	149 hr.	76.2%	177 hr.	31.3%
Ethyl oleate	149	74.3	160	30.7
Ethyl stearate	156	46.9	184	31.3
Liquid paraffin	191	79.8	191	46.6
Liquid paraffin + ethyl oleate	192	82.1	192	35.7
Liquid paraffin + ethyl stearate	177	60.9	185	34.8
Liquid paraffin + glyceryl monolaurate	170	68.7	177	13.6

DISCUSSION

It is apparent from the results so far obtained that the cause of deterioration of vitamin-A is due to a sort of oxidation in the molecule with the formation of a peroxide like body (type VI). The formation of such peroxide body has been lowered by about 50% on addition of an antioxidant in liquid paraffin *cum* vitamin-A system (vide Table III). From Table I it will be noticed that the loss of vitamin in ethyl oleate, adjuvated with 0.05% dimethylhydroquinone, is 75.1% after 177 hours' aeration and compares well with the system containing no antioxidant, whereas monomethyl hydroquinone (0.05%) protects 69.7% of the vitamin-A potency. From this and also from the protective action of propyl gallate (cf. part I, *loc. cit.*) it appears that for exerting an antioxidant function the compound must contain one or more free phenolic hydroxyl groups.

The function of the hydroxy antioxidant most probably lies in the formation of a complex of the type (VII) and thereby preventing the vitamin-A alcohol molecule from absorbing oxygen at the unsaturated linkage present in the β -ionone ring (the susceptible bond of the molecule) to form a peroxide of the nature (VI). This is :

FIG. 1

Curve I—Liquid paraffin + vitamin-A
 II— " + " + antioxidant
 III— " + " + " + oleic acid

what substantiated by the fact that the loss of vitamin-A potency comes down to 44.6% from 79.8% after 191 hours' aeration when the vitamin in saturated diluent (liquid paraffin) contains an antioxidant (cf. Table II and the curves I and II, Fig 1).

But during the formation of the complex of the type (VII), where the antioxidant becomes bound with the vitamin-A molecule, there would be gradual shortage of the antioxidant till it is exhausted and would thereby cease to exert its antioxygenic function any more. In order to maintain its function the antioxidant needs regeneration from the complex by some hydrogen donating substance when the vitamin-A also will be free again to exert its characteristic reaction. The continuity of the supply of antioxidant to the system and the maintenance of vitamin-A will then remain practically unaffected. Such regeneration of the antioxidant may be seen from Table II and also from the curves II and III of Fig. 1, where trace of oleic acid as well as water, both of which have ionisable hydrogen atom individually, helps the antioxidant to maintain the vitamin-A potency in liquid paraffin to a higher degree than the system containing no such hydrogen donor.

It is interesting to note that the loss of vitamin-A in liquid paraffin system containing antioxidant and some hydrogen donating substance compares well with the systems containing esters or glycerides with antioxidant (vide Tables I, II and V).

The above postulate on the mode of function of the antioxidant and its regeneration may be extended to the case of esters or glycerides. In presence of an antioxidant an ester or glyceride, natural or synthetic, seems to play a part like that of oleic acid when added to a solution of vitamin-A in liquid paraffin. From the data in Table V it will be evident that a similar inhibition is obtained when the vitamin is dissolved in a pure ester or glyceride with an antioxidant. This inhibiting action may be attributed to the incipient formation of free acid in the system which in turn regenerates the antioxidant from the complex of the type (VII). The mode of reaction of the antioxidant with vitamin-A molecule may be represented as follows :

The vitamin-A alcohol (type I) containing conjugated double bonded systems may undergo a prototropic change and in the return of the proton the 5 and 14 carbon atoms of the conjugated system may become activated (cf. type V) and form a peroxide of the type (VI). In presence of hydroxy-phenolic antioxidant it may, however, form a complex (type VII). The latter under the influence of a hydrogen donating substance would undergo fission to regenerate the antioxidant and the vitamin to play their respective role.

The replacement of the mobile hydrogen atom of the vitamin-A alcohol by esterification would tend to lower its prototropic change and consequently its susceptibility to receive an electronic charge. This would prevent the formation of peroxide-like body of the type (VI). Most probably it is for this reason that preparations made with vitamin-A acetate in ethyl stearate or even with ethyl oleate without the presence of antioxidant retain the vitamin-A potency on aeration to a degree comparable to preparations made with vitamin-A in alcohol in presence of antioxidant (vide Tables IV and V).

It has been noticed that the vitamin-A alcohol, when dissolved in glycerides or esters, loses a portion of its potency, whereas in the case of vitamin-A acetate no such initial loss has been experienced. In liquid paraffin medium too, no initial loss is noticed with vitamin-A alcohol. It appears that the antioxidant is not functioning to react with the peroxide already formed in the system but exerts its influence to prevent the further formation of the peroxide. The reported stability of Neo-vitamin-A may also be studied from this angle. Further investigations are being continued.

CONCLUSION

The antioxidant must contain a phenolic 'OH' and its antioxygenic function is enhanced by suitable hydrogen donator. The vitamin-A alcohol is susceptible to the easy formation of a peroxide which is retarded by the presence of an antioxidant. The vitamin-A ester, however, is less susceptible to oxidation.